

2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde – Formaldehyde Copolymers and their Ion-exchange Properties

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Copolymers were synthesised by the condensation of 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (2,4-DB) and formaldehyde (F) in the presence of H_2SO_4 (1.5 M) and HCl (2 M) as catalyst with varied molar ratios of the reacting monomers. The copolymers were characterised by ir spectra, $\bar{M}_n$ was determined by vapour pressure osmometry as well as by non-aqueous conductometric titrations, elemental analyses and TGA. Viscosity measurements of the solutions of the copolymer samples were carried out in dimethylformamide. Chelation ion-exchange properties have also been studied employing the batch equilibration method.

CHELATION ion-exchange resins prepared by copolycondensation of 8-hydroxyquinoline or phenol derivatives like *o*-aminophenol, β -resorcylic acid or resorcinol with formaldehyde have been reported^{1,2}. The salicylic acid/*p*-chloro-(bromo)-formaldehyde polymers has been reported to show a chelation ion-exchange capacity³⁻⁵. Poly(oxine-alkylene) have been reported as ion-exchangers⁶. Blasius and Kynast⁷ prepared the chelating ion-exchange resin by condensation of *o*-hydroxyphenoxyacetic acid with catechol and formaldehyde. Resacetophenone – formaldehyde and resacetophenoneoxime – formaldehyde polymers has been reported as ion-exchangers^{8,9}.

In the present paper we report the synthesis, characterisation of 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde – formaldehyde (2,4-DB – F) copolymers and study of their selectivity and capacity in the ion-exchange reaction.

Experimental

All the reagents were of high purity. DMF and $POCl_3$ were used after distillation. Pyridine and methanol were purified by conventional chemical

methods. 2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde was obtained by treating a solution of resorcinol in DMF with $POCl_3$ at 0 – 5° in an ice-bath^{10,11}.

Preparation of copolymers: 2,4-DB (0.1 mol) and 1.5 M H_2SO_4 (24 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 1 h and then polymerised with 37% formaldehyde (0.1 mol). The contents were refluxed with stirring at 85 – 7° for 6 h in a water-bath. The resulting solid brickred coloured product was filtered, washed with large amount of boiling water and dried. Dried copolymer was soxhlet-extracted with solvent ether to remove unreacted 2,4-DB. The copolymer was also prepared as described above using 2 M HCl (48 ml) instead of H_2SO_4 . Different copolymer samples were prepared employing different molar ratios of formaldehyde and 2,4-DB. The reaction details and the elemental analyses of the copolymers are given in Table I.

Analytical methods and physical measurements: Elemental analysis was carried out on a Coleman C-H analyser. Conductivity of the polymer samples in pyridine was measured¹² using a Konduktoskop Metrohm Harisau conductometer. Number average molecular weights ($\bar{M}_n$) of all the

TABLE I—CHARACTERISATION OF COPOLYMERS

Copolymer	2,4-DB mol	Reactants			Colour	Yield %	Analysis*, wt%	
		37% Formaldehyde (F) mol	1.5 M H_2SO_4 ml	2 M HCl ml			C	H
2,4-DB – F-1	0.1	0.1	24	—	Brick red	56	64.5	4.10
2,4-DB – F-2	0.1	0.2	24	—	Brick red	52	63.4	3.89
2,4-DB – F-3	0.1	0.3	24	—	Brick red	49	64.9	3.96
2,4-DB – F-4	0.1	0.4	24	—	Brick red	46	64.6	4.08
2,4-DB – F-5	0.1	0.1	—	48	Brick red	55	64.2	3.99
2,4-DB – F-6	0.1	0.2	—	48	Brick red	51	64.0	3.90
2,4-DB – F-7	0.1	0.3	—	48	Brick red	48	63.8	3.95
2,4-DB – F-8	0.1	0.4	—	48	Brick red	45	63.2	4.05

*Empirical formula for repeating unit, $C_8H_8O_2$; MW of repeating unit, 150; Calcd. for repeat unit: C, 64.0; H, 4.0%.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISATION OF COPOLYMERS

Copolymer	VPO	$\bar{M}_n$		Percentage weight loss at different temp. in air (°C.)						Energy of activation kcal mol ⁻¹
		Conductometric titration	$[\eta] \times 10^3$ dl g ⁻¹	100	200	300	400	500	600	
2,4-DB-F-1	2 138	2 199	5.20	0	1	10	40	70	70	5.10
2,4-DB-F-2	1 732	1 786	4.28	0	1	11	85	85	85	10.93
2,4-DB-F-3	1 003	1 050	3.13	0	1	8	35	97	97	6.42
2,4-DB-F-4	950	994	3.09	0	0.5	6	87	90	90	18.63
2,4-DB-F-5	2 406	2 475	6.35	0	0.5	13	73	74	74	17.76
2,4-DB-F-6	1 725	1 773	4.25	0	0.5	23	86	88	88	13.66
2,4-DB-F-7	1 993	1 465	4.10	0	2	25	86	86	86	23.90
2,4-DB-F-8	1 109	1 162	3.50	0	1	17	87	87	87	14.56

copolymers were estimated by vapour pressure osmometry using DMF as solvent and benzil as calibrant at 71°.

Viscometric measurements of the solutions of the copolymer samples were carried out using a Ubbelohde viscometer at 35 ± 0.1°. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analyses of all the copolymer samples were carried out on a Du Pont-951 instrument in air at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹.

The batch equilibrium method was adopted to study the ion-exchanging properties^{13,14}. The evaluation of the influence of different electrolytes on the metal uptake by the copolymer, the rate of metal uptake under specified conditions and the distribution of various metal ions at different pH values were carried out following the procedures described earlier¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

The probable structure of copolymers have been determined on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data. Copolymer samples were in powder form having brickred colour and were soluble in pyridine and DMF. The copolymers did not melt upto 250°. The number average molecular weights ($\bar{M}_n$) of all the copolymer samples were determined by non-aqueous conductometric titration in pyridine using sodium methoxide (NaOMe) in pyridine as titrant and $\bar{M}_n$ values of the copolymer samples were calculated following a prescribed method^{13,16}. $\bar{M}_n$ of copolymer samples was also determined by vapour pressure osmometry (VPO) in DMF at 71°. The values are presented in Table 2. The values of $\bar{M}_n$ obtained by both the methods are in good agreement. The copolymer sample obtained using equimolar proportion of the two monomers (2,4-DB and F) has the highest molecular weight. The viscometric measurements in DMF were carried out and plots of reduced viscosity vs concentration (4 to 2.15 g dl⁻¹) were made for each set of data. The intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ is reported in Table 2. As expected, the copolymers having higher $\bar{M}_n$ have higher values of $[\eta]$.

All the copolymers reveal similar ir spectra. A broad band appearing at 3 100–3 600 cm⁻¹ is due to OH stretching. The strong band at 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and a weak band around 2 720 cm⁻¹ indicate an intramolecular H-bond¹⁷. The bands at 2 930, 1 480 and 735 cm⁻¹ suggest the presence of methylene bridges^{17,18}. The phenolic OH in-plane bending and stretching are observed in the ranges 1 240–1 250 and 1 340–1 350 cm⁻¹ respectively. Bands appearing in the region 1 010–1 190 cm⁻¹ are attributed to C–H in-plane bending¹⁹. The bands at 1 470–1 600 cm⁻¹ are attributed to C=C stretching (aromatic) vibrations²⁰. The out-of-plane C–H bending band around 910 cm⁻¹ is due to penta-substituted phenyl ring²¹. The band around 855 cm⁻¹ is due to 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted phenyl ring²¹. The band around 820 cm⁻¹ is due to 1,2,3,4-tetrasubstituted phenyl ring²¹. From ir spectral and analytical data, the following structure for the copolymer is suggested.

The results of TGA (Table 2) reveal that each copolymer sample undergoes degradation in single step are thermally stable upto 250°. All the copolymers undergo thermal degradation at slower rate in the begining upto 300° and the decomposition is complete at 500° where 74–97% weight loss is observed. Copolymers prepared using equimolar proportion of reactants are thermally more stable. The Broido method²² was applied to the TG data to determine the energy of activation.

Ion-exchanging properties: The results of the batch equilibrium study carried out with the copolymer sample 2,4-DB-F-1 are presented in Tables 3–5. The data (Table 3) reveal that the amount of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, UO₂²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions taken up by a given amount of the copolymer sample increases with the increasing concentration of ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ and decreases with the increasing concentration of SO₄²⁻ ion, whereas uptake of Co³⁺ and Mn²⁺ ions by the

above copolymer increases with the decreasing concentration of ClO_4^- , NO_3^- , Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions. This may be explained in terms of stability constants of complexes which Fe^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} form with these ligands²³⁻²⁵. Sulphate might form strong complexes, while perchlorate, nitrate and chloride might form weak complexes with Fe^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. Whereas Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} ions might form strong complexes with ClO_4^- , Cl^- and NO_3^- and hence their metal uptake increases with the decreasing concentration of electrolyte. This type of trend has also been observed by other investigators^{5,8,11,26,27}.

TABLE 3—EVALUATION OF INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES IN THE UPTAKE OF METAL IONS

Metal* ion	Added electrolyte* mol dm ⁻³	pH	× 10 mmol of metal ion uptake in presence of			
			NaClO ₄	NaCl	NaNO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₄
Cu ²⁺	0.01	5.5	0.26	0.14	0.20	0.30
	0.05		0.39	0.16	0.24	0.29
	0.10		0.42	0.19	0.25	0.26
	0.50		0.47	0.29	0.28	0.24
	1.00		0.50	0.40	0.32	0.10
Ni ²⁺	0.01	5.5	0.18	0.14	0.17	0.29
	0.05		0.30	0.15	0.20	0.28
	0.10		0.32	0.16	0.22	0.24
	0.50		0.36	0.18	0.24	0.22
	1.00		0.40	0.20	0.28	0.12
Co ²⁺	0.01	5.5	0.32	0.30	0.26	0.22
	0.05		0.29	0.25	0.21	0.21
	0.10		0.255	0.23	0.18	0.19
	0.50		0.18	0.21	0.16	0.18
	1.00		0.16	0.20	0.15	0.16
Mn ²⁺	0.01	5.5	0.24	0.22	0.24	0.31
	0.05		0.22	0.18	0.22	0.29
	0.10		0.18	0.12	0.20	0.25
	0.50		0.15	0.11	0.17	0.21
	1.00		0.11	0.10	0.12	0.16
UO ₂ ²⁺	0.01	4.00	0.24	0.20	0.21	0.28
	0.05		0.30	0.21	0.24	0.26
	0.10		0.35	0.24	0.42	0.25
	0.50		0.42	0.27	0.50	0.23
	1.00		0.65	0.32	0.58	0.21
Fe ³⁺	0.10	2.75	0.10	0.06	0.31	0.24
	0.05		0.23	0.08	0.36	0.22
	0.10		0.25	0.10	0.39	0.20
	0.50		0.30	0.18	0.41	0.13
	1.00		0.33	0.29	0.45	0.04

*M(NO₃)₃ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (2 ml) **25 ml; 24 h (equilibrium state)

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF RATES OF METAL ION UPTAKE[†]

Metal ion	% Amount of metal ions taken up [‡] (t, h)							
	0.5	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Cu ²⁺	35.0	49.0	65.2	70.00	74.8	88.0	99.0	—
Ni ²⁺	38.0	42.0	48.5	62.8	69.5	85.0	99.5	99.5
Co ²⁺	20.0	32.0	36.0	49.0	62.5	73.0	85.0	98.0
Mn ²⁺	25.0	35.0	39.0	52.0	64.0	75.0	85.0	99.0
UO ₂ ²⁺	50.0	80.2	87.4	98.0	100.0	—	—	—
Fe ³⁺	40.0	75.5	88.0	97.0	99.0	—	—	—

†M(NO₃)₃ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (2 ml), NaNO₃ = 1 mol dm⁻³ (25 ml); pH = 3.0, Room temp.

‡ $\frac{\text{mmol of metal ion adsorbed} \times 100}{\text{mmol of metal ion adsorbed at equilibrium}}$

TABLE 5—DISTRIBUTION RATIOS (D) OF METAL IONS AS A FUNCTION OF pH

Metal ion	Distribution ratio at pH						
	1.5	2.00	2.5	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0
Cu ²⁺	—	—	12.10	24.50	43.50	125.90	190.47
Ni ²⁺	—	—	39.81	50.10	63.00	94.10	162.79
Co ²⁺	—	—	20.00	35.50	50.00	65.30	81.10
Mn ²⁺	—	—	—	10.0	40.5	52.5	63.88
UO ₂ ²⁺	30.5	92.8	160.00	260.00	318.68	—	—
Fe ³⁺	50.6	158.40	290.32	—	—	—	—

*D = $\frac{\text{mmol metal ion taken up by 1 g copolymer}}{\text{mmol metal ion present in 1 ml of solution phase}}$

[M(NO₃)₃] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (2 ml), [NaNO₃] = 1 mol dm⁻³ (25 ml), Room temp.; Time = 24 h (equilibrium state).

The rate of metal adsorption of 2,4-DB-F-1 was determined to find out the shortest period of time for which equilibration could be carried out while operating as close to equilibrium conditions as possible. Table 4 shows the dependence of the rate of metal ion uptake on the nature of the metal. Fe³⁺ and UO₂²⁺ ions required slightly more than 3 h for the establishment of equilibrium while Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ions required ~6 h. In the experiments with solution containing UO₂²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions more than 70% equilibrium was established in the first hour. Mn²⁺ and Co²⁺ ions required almost 7 h for equilibrium. The rate of metal ion uptake follows the order UO₂²⁺, Fe³⁺ > Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺, Mn²⁺.

The effect of pH on the amount of metal ion distributed between two phases can be explained by the results shown in Table 5. The results indicate that the relative amount of metal ions taken up by the copolymer increases with the increasing pH of the medium. The study was carried out upto a definite pH value for the particular metal ion to prevent hydrolysis of the metal ions at higher pH. UO₂²⁺ ion is taken up more selectively than any other metal ion under study. Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ions are taken up more selectively by the copolymer than Co²⁺ and Mn²⁺ ions. The lower distribution ratio of Fe³⁺ than UO₂²⁺ may be attributed to steric hindrance imposed by polymer matrix which inhibits the completion of the Fe^{III} d² sp³ hybrid with 3 mers of 2,4-DB-F as opposed to the formation of the chelate of Fe^{III} with monomeric 2,4-DB. UO₂²⁺ only needs 2 mers of 2,4-DB-F for completion of its coordination requirement which is easily accomplished¹⁸. Co²⁺ and Mn²⁺ have low distribution ratio in the pH range 4–6. This could be attributed to the low stability constants in the pH range 4–6, i.e. weak ligand stabilisation energy of the metal complexes^{24,25}. The possible order of selectivity of a cation-exchange resin for the divalent metal ions would be Pd > Cu > Ni > Co > Zn > Cd > Fe > Mn > Mg²⁺. In the present study, the observed order of distribution ratios of divalent ions measured in the pH range 3–6 was found to be UO₂²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Mn²⁺. The results of this study are helpful in selecting the optimum pH for the selective uptake of a metal ion from a mixture of different ions. For example,

the results suggest the optimum pH to be 2.5 for the separation of Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , where the distribution ratio D of Cu^{2+} is 12.1 and that of Fe^{3+} is 290.32.

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